

BUILDING AN EFFECTIVE MODEL OF FORMING PRAGMATIC COMPETENCE BASED ON CORPUS TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract

Within the framework of this research, which is considered one of the tasks of building an effective model of the formation of pragmatic competence based on corpus technologies, in order to create our own educational model, it is necessary to determine the methodological basis, preliminary conditions, and the main goal of the research.

Key words: corpus technologies, formation of pragmatic competence, methodical model, linguistic-didactic potential, socio-cultural component.

Let's move on to studying the preliminary conditions for creating a methodical model of forming students' pragmatic competence based on corpus technologies. As the initial conditions indicated above, we distinguish the following three ideas and rules. The first of them is a social order for training students who have acquired pragmatic skills in a foreign language. The second prerequisite for the creation of this methodological model is the need to comply with the requirements of SESHE (state educational standards for higher education) of the bachelor's degree. It is appropriate to consider the existence of conflicts between the linguistic and didactic potential of corpus technologies and their use in the formation of pragmatic competence as the third initial/preliminary condition.

The next stage of creating a methodological model is to build its theoretical block. This element includes the principles and approaches used in the teaching process. A principle is a certain integral starting point/point in the learning process. The approach incorporates various principles and directs the teaching process in one direction or another. From here comes the importance of selecting approaches and principles in a particular methodological model.

Therefore, we consider it correct to include the following approaches within this research: a) communicative-cognitive; b) systematicity; c) personal-activity-based and g) compensatory principles. Let's take a closer look at each approach, justifying OUR choices.

Communicative-cognitive approach (Shchepilova A.V., 2003) requires a certain (some kind of) balance between the development of speech skills in the studied language and the acquisition of theoretical knowledge in it. This approach has a communicative-cognitive orientation, and this is its main principle. The cognitive component of this principle is intended to activate (use) knowledge about linguistic (linguistic) systems for the process of language learning, to give it the property of understanding/consciousness/meaningfulness. According to scientists, such orientation is effective due to the use of linguistic (linguistic) experience. From here comes the principle of philologizing (linguisticization), which requires the activation of knowledge about the mother tongue, literature, linguistics, other languages and cultures in the process of teaching a foreign language. The theoretical aspect studies the language system as a part of human culture that is projected into foreign language teaching. There are several ways to carry out philologicalization at this level. First, language as a system can be studied from the perspective of its development in several directions: historical, grammatical, social and other. Secondly, in teaching a foreign language, the knowledge of the mother tongue and/or previously learned languages can be used as a certain (some kind of) basis.

Thirdly, the socio-cultural component can actively participate in the formation of communicative competence of persons learning a foreign language. As for the practical importance of philologizing, it consists in the use of various texts. So, in our opinion, the combination (application) of communicative and cognitive orientation aspects creates an effective model for the formation of pragmatic competence.

Any system of teaching is based on a certain system. The unsystematic nature of teaching seriously complicates the progress of students and reduces their level of motivation. That is why we consider it necessary/obligatory to include a systematic approach in our proposed model of forming pragmatic competence based on corpus technologies. The systematic approach that appeared in the pedagogy of our country in the 1960s organizes and structures the teaching methodology. Scientist I.V. Blauberg, who is considered one of the proponents of the systematic approach, proposed a component composition of this approach. Integrativeness was proposed by the scientist as its first element. According to the author, this parameter is the main/key parameter and requires a certain integrity of the system. Other principles of the systemic approach are distinguished from integrative ones. The principle of hierarchy (the existence of

a hierarchy) requires the structured dependence/subordination of the elements of the system. This is where the principle of structure comes from. This principle requires the organization of the system according to certain rules. Plurality is the ultimate principle. Demonstration of this principle consists in using different cloud models (different cloud of models) to study a particular system and its individual components.

The person-activity-based approach was adopted to study within the framework of the application of the components that make up the two components of its name. The first of them - the person-based (focused) component requires studying each student as an individual, taking into account all social (sociological) and psychological variables. There is no doubt that such an approach helps the teacher to build the teaching process in accordance with the personal characteristics/qualities of the students.

Competency-based approach is one of the most common approaches to foreign language teaching. This approach is included in the documents regulating educational activities at various levels. The main/key goal of the competency-based approach is to form certain competencies in students (Zimnyaya I.A., 2003). There are many types of competencies included in the competency-based approach. The first group of competences is called universal competences (UK). Multicultural competences are a set of skills and competencies within and across cultures. The second group of competencies consists of general professional competencies (UKK). These competencies consist of skills and competencies formed during the educational process and correspond to the amount of knowledge in a specific subject. The third type of competencies is called professional (professional) competencies (KK). This type of competence enables a professional to be successful in their professional/professional activities and includes knowledge and experience.

A competency-based approach has a number of advantages/advantages that make it attractive to use. First, it consists in the use of practical activities more than theoretical activities, which (practical activities) are ultimately more important in professional activities. Moreover, a competency-based approach allows solving/doing the same task in different ways. This means (leads to) a higher level of creativity and individualization in teaching. In addition, this approach encouraged students to be autonomous/autonomous, developing their inner sense of inquiry and research activity. We consider these signs to be very important in the formation of pragmatic competence based on corpus technologies.

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